

Rural to urban transition of risk factors propensity for cardiovascular disease in Jharkhand, India

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Abstract

Background: Risk factor evaluation for cardiovascular disease (CVD) is an important part of reducing the heavy burden of CVD. This research demonstrates the spatial differences in the incidence of CVD risk factors in rural and urban areas of Jharkhand, India.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey-based epidemiological study was conducted using a structured questionnaire formulated on ICMR guidelines, which mainly compared CVD risk factors of rural and urban populations in Jharkhand.

Results: Obesity and hypertension affect 41.46% and 31.95% of the population in Jharkhand, respectively. Obesity and hypertension were roughly four and two times more prevalent in cities than in rural areas. Urban areas have a greater frequency of prediabetes (23.54%) than rural areas (16.12%). Multiple logistic regression analysis (MLRA) revealed a significant (9-fold) increase in obesity risk and high mean arterial pressure (MAP) values for urban versus rural people. The MLRA of all CVD risk factor variables revealed that those who were drinkers or daily smokers had an almost twofold higher probability of developing hypertension or obesity. Overall, persons above 40 years of age demonstrated a 3-4-fold propensity to develop obesity, prediabetes, or diabetes than those below 40 years of age.

Conclusion: Among the aggregate 41.46% of obese and 31.95% hypertensive people in Jharkhand, MLR analysis revealed that urban individuals were 9 and 8 times more likely than rural individuals to develop obesity and hypertension, respectively. Research with a larger sample size will back up our claim and aid in disease burden management across regions.

Keywords: Cardiovascular disease risk factors, Hypertension, Mean arterial pressure, Fasting blood sugar, Body mass index, Obesity, Diabetes, Rural, Urban, India

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a group of heart and blood vessel disorders that include coronary heart disease, peripheral arterial disease, congenital heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, and other conditions (1,2). CVD might be asymptomatic for a long time, cause symptoms at an advanced stage, or even result in

abrupt death (3). The most prevalent cause of heart attacks and strokes is the accumulation of fat deposits, known as thrombus, on the inner walls of blood vessels. Strokes can also be caused by blood vessel bleeding or blood clots, which occur as a result of a sudden increase in blood pressure in the brain.

In 2016, CVDs were the leading cause of death (31%) worldwide, accounting for 17.9 million deaths (4). In 2015, 37% of all premature deaths (before the age of 70) from noncommunicable diseases were caused by CVDs (5, 6). Over three-quarters of CVD deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries, such as India (7). Hypertension, diabetes, and hyperlipidemia are commonly associated with heart attacks and strokes, as are a poor diet and obesity, physical inactivity, and dangerous tobacco and alcohol use.

Population explosion, rapid urbanization-related ecological imbalance, disparity in minimum health care availability between rural and urban people, lack of health awareness programs, vulnerable ethnicity of South Asian lineage, physical inactivity, and a lingering mentality to address health issues are just a few of the factors that have made India the most vulnerable to CVD (7).

In India, the age-adjusted CVD death rate for men and women was 386 and 283 per lakh, respectively, significantly higher than in the United States and most of Europe (8). According to the Registrar General of India, the prevalence of coronary heart disease has increased from 1% to 10% in urban areas and $\pm 1\%$ to 6% in rural areas over the past 60 years (9). A substantial link between CVD risk and fast urbanization was discovered in 2010 (10).

Along with traditional CVD risk factors, other emerging risks include family history of CVD, C reactive protein and homocysteine levels, menopause, high-risk ethnicity, a lack of fruits and vegetables, and a high consumption of table salt and oil (11, 12).

It was suggested that about 109 candidate genes identified through genome-wide association studies may also contribute to early CVD (13). The combined gene-environment interaction has a bigger influence than either factor alone. Non-modifiable risk factors (NMRF), such as age, gender, and ethnicity, make a population more sensitive to CVD (14); however, many, such as obesity, hypertension, food and drink preferences, alcohol intake, smoking, and so on, are modifiable risk factors (15). Nutritional transition has been identified as a major contributor to CVD, particularly in third-world countries (16).

According to the American Heart Association (AHA), identifying individual risk factors, lowering evaluated risks, assisting with lifestyle changes, taking appropriate medication on time, and so on can all directly reduce risk factors (17, 18). Understanding the risk factor's prevalence could help save countless lives (19).

Jharkhand became a separate state from Bihar in 2000 due to its strong aboriginal population and cultural diversity. In the last 20 years or more, a major change in lifestyle has occurred as a result of accelerated urbanization, resulting in changes in all aspects of life, including the onset of several noncommunicable diseases (NCD), including CVD. Since almost nothing has been done to

assess risk factors in these close-to-nature populations until now, it is time to get an overall picture of the said risk factor prevalence in people living in spatially different locations of the state with differences in culture and topography. As a first step in reducing the CVD burden in India, a survey of CVD risk factor prevalence in two distinct geographic and socioeconomic areas of the state of Jharkhand was launched.

Material and Methods:

Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted on a few rural and urban groups in Ranchi, Khunti, and Bokaro districts of Jharkhand.

Sampling Technique

The study participants were chosen using a multistage random selection process. The initial stage entailed randomly selecting a few rural communities or distinct urban districts. The second stage consisted of randomly picking households from each community. In the third stage, one or two persons aged 18 or older who had no indications or symptoms of CVD were picked from selected households.

Population studied

Rural Jharkhand is dominated by tribals, although non-tribals predominate in urban regions. In this study, Ranchi and Patki were considered urban regions, while Saharatoli, Kudlum of Khunti district, Karkat of Ranchi district, Merudaru, Pithoria, and Bhudhan Gora villages of Bokaro district were considered rural (Figure 1).

Figure 1 displays all of the researched locations in three districts (Ranchi, Khunti, and Bokaro) of the Indian state of Jharkhand. People from Saharatoli Torpa, Karra-Kudlum, villages in Khunti district, Merudaru, Pithoria, Tenughat, and Bhudhan Gora villages in Bokaro district, and Karkat in Ranchi district were classified as rural. The survey of CVD risk factors was conducted in urban areas such as the Patki region of Bokaro, Bariatu, Booty More, Kusum Vihar, Jai Prakash Nagar, RIMS, Khelgaon, Doranda, Kokar, and Morabadi sections of Ranchi.

Areas researched in Ranchi included Baryatu, Booty More, Kusum Vihar, Jai Prakash Nagar Baryatu, Rims Baryatu, Khelgaon, Doranda, Morabadi, and Kokar. The villages in Bokaro district were referred to collectively in this study as the rest of Bokaro (ROB). All participants provided written informed consent. The institutional ethics committee at the Rajendra Institute of Medical Science in Ranchi, Jharkhand, accepted the study.

Sample Size

In epidemiological studies, features of a small sample are used to make generalizations about the community. The sample size is an important consideration. To calculate the sample size, the Central Limit Theorem for Proportions is employed.

The following formula was used to compute the sample size:

$$n = \frac{Z_{\alpha/2}^2 P(1 - P)}{\varepsilon^2}$$

where ε is the margin of error. The choice of the margin of error is determined by the population percentage, or more specifically the prevalence rate of a trait. $Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$ for $\alpha=0.05$.

Many coronary disease risk factor indicators are being examined in this study, including body mass index (BMI), mean arterial pressure (MAP), and blood sugar levels. High quantities of these are considered common in any population. To apply the above method, we must assume a pre-existing population proportion that is evident from previous research. The margin of error is conveniently set at one-fourth or one-fifth of the population proportion.

The proportion of high BMI is roughly 16% on average, and high MAP is 20% on average, but these figures vary by area. For these values, the sample size is 573,384. In this investigation, 832 people were recruited (sample size), which was slightly larger than the required number to better evaluate the effect of many physiological variables on these CVD risk factor measurements.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Only asymptomatic male and female individuals aged 18 to 80 years were recruited in general, and they were not using any prescribed CVD medication(s). Individuals above the age of 80, pregnant women, and people with physical disabilities were all excluded from the study.

Data collection

Data were obtained using a modified cardiovascular risk factor assessment structured questionnaire as recommended by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), which contained three key fields: (i) anthropometric information such as weight, height, blood pressure, and so on. (ii) Behavioral risk factor profiles, such as excessive salt and oil consumption, alcohol and tobacco use, physical activity, and so on; and (iii) biochemical characteristics, such as blood sugar and lipid profile. Random sugar data was collected exclusively from Karkat village, Patki in urban Bokaro, and all areas of Ranchi city excluding the Doranda area.

Measurement of blood pressure and anthropometric variables

A manual sphygmomanometer (BPDFL-231, Diamond, Deluxe) was used to measure blood pressure in the right hand while completely relaxed. Prior to the actual survey, the instrument was tested for reliability on three persons.

Weight and height measurement

A digital weighing machine of a maximum 150 kg capacity (error +/- 0.1 kg) was used. Non-elastic measuring tape fixed on a wooden board with a least count of 0.1 cm was used to take the height of the subjects for BMI calculation.

Statistical analysis

Cross-tabulations of the initial data set were used to obtain descriptive statistics. Multiple Logistic Regression Analysis (MLRA) was used to assess the effects of age, gender, alcohol consumption, smoking, and physical activity (all independent variables) on hypertension, obesity, and high fasting blood sugar (FBG). All statistical tests were performed with a significance threshold of 5% using R version 3.6.3.

Definition of risk factors and diagnostic criteria Obesity

Body mass index (BMI) was computed by dividing the participants' body weight in kg by their height squared in meters. Asian guidelines classify BMI levels less than 25 kg/m² as non-obese, whereas values of 25 kg/m² or higher are deemed obese.

Hypertension

MAP, an alternate indicator of blood pressure grade per single cardiac cycle, was derived using the equation $MAP = DBP + 1/3 (SBP - DBP)$, which took into account both systolic (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP). MAP levels more than 100 were termed hypertensive. Values above 70 and below 100 were termed normotensive.

Prediabetes and Diabetes

Random sugar values ≥ 140 to ≤ 199 mg/dL were classified as pre-diabetic, whereas those above that threshold (200) were diabetic. Blood sugar levels less than 140 mg/dL were considered as normal.

Results

Age, Gender, and Ethnicity based population studied

In this study of 832 participants (487 from urban and 345 from rural parts of Jharkhand), two distinct socio-geographical (rural and urban) communities exhibited

significant disparities in CVD risk factor prevalence. Tables 1A, 1B, and 1C show the regional gender ratio, age distribution, and two ethnic groupings of the overall population. The survey participants in Ranchi and Patki, Bokaro, were primarily from non-tribal groups, whereas tribal people dominated rural areas.

Table 1A displays the number of male and female participants drawn from urban and rural areas in three districts of Jharkhand (value in parenthesis indicates %). Table 1B shows the number of two age categories, 'below 40 years' and 'more than 40 years', drawn from the rural and urban populations surveyed. Table 1C shows the number of two ethnic groupings (tribal and non-tribal) investigated in rural and urban populations (values in parenthesis indicate %).

Comparison of Urban and Rural Areas

Obesity rates in rural regions were 16.52% (57 out of 345), which was significantly lower than the 59.13% (288 out of 487) in cities. Among the overall 31.97% (266 out of 832) of the hypertension population, urban subjects had a much larger percentage of hypertensive people (41.47%) than rural subjects (18.55%). Random blood sugar tests were performed on 155 rural and 327 urban patients, for a total of 482 out of 832 research participants. Table 2 shows that 24.51% of rural persons and 31.19% of urban people had prediabetes or diabetes. The number of persons drawn from rural or urban populations, with data broken down by gender and age group, as well as the number of people affected or unaffected by obesity, hypertension, and diabetes (numbers in parenthesis indicate percentages) can be seen in table 2.

MLRA of the whole population

MLR analysis revealed that tribal populations have a lower risk of developing obesity or hypertension than non-tribal populations. Males were substantially more likely than females to acquire obesity and hypertension. Participants over 40 were four times more likely to develop obesity (OR = 3.73, 95% Confidence Interval (C. I) = 2.72-5.17) and nearly one and a half times more likely to develop hypertension (OR = 1.31, 95% C. I = 0.98-1.76), as evidenced by their high MAP values (see table 3). Urban persons were shown to be more susceptible to acquiring hypertension (OR = 2.39, 95% C.I = 1.24-4.63) and obesity (OR = 1.22, 95% C.I = 0.57-2.52) than rural people (table 3). Table 3 shows that 1) the odds of having high MAP for the 'above 40 years age group' increase almost 1.31 times those of the 'below 40 years age group'; 2) the odds of being obese increase almost 3.73 times for the 'above 40 years age group' than the 'below 40 years age group'. Hence Age plays a major role; 3) Urban people have a 2.39 times higher risk of having hypertensive (an elevated MAP value) than rural persons. Hence

Urbanization has a major role; 4) The odds of having high MAP (signifies hypertensive) for tribal people decrease by 0.70 times from that of non-tribal people; and 5) The odds of being obese for tribal people decrease by 0.84 times from that of the non-tribal people. Hence ethnicity plays a crucial factor.

Pre-diabetic & Diabetic risk factor status in Urban and Rural populations

Blood glucose levels were measured for 482 people out of 832 total subjects, including participation from both communities. In MLR analysis, the tribal population had a much lower risk of developing diabetes but a slightly higher risk of developing pre-diabetes than the nontribal group. The odds of having pre-diabetes or diabetes were almost fourfold higher in the 'over 40 years' age group than in the 'below 40 years' age group, with OR values of 4.09 and 3.59 at the 95% significant level. There was a significant 2.26-fold and an insignificant 1.46-fold increase in susceptibility to prediabetes and diabetes in urban versus rural populations (table 4). Table 4 shows that 1) the odds of being pre-diabetic and diabetic increase nearly 4 and 3.5 times from that of the 'below 40 years age group', and 2) the odds of being pre-diabetic and diabetic increased almost 2 and 1.5 times, respectively. Hence Age and urbanization are significant risk factors for being diabetes or prediabetic.

MLR analysis of Khunti & Rest of Bokaro villages as Rural with Ranchi and Patki of Bokaro as Urban communities

The urban population (Ranchi metropolitan regions and Patki) was shown to be nearly twice as susceptible to acquiring high MAP values or hypertension as the rural population (Khunti and ROB villages) (table 5). The urban population likewise had a negligible 1.32-fold higher risk of being obese than the rural population. Again, persons over 40 had a much higher risk of getting obesity and hypertension than those under 40. Overall, girls had a much lower risk of becoming obesity than males (table 5). Table 5 shows that 1) the odds of having a high MAP value increased almost 2.37 times in urban areas over rural areas; 2) the odds of being obese and hypertensive increased almost 3.66 and 1.36 times in the 'above 40 years age group' compared to the 'below 40 years age group'; and 3) the odds of having a high MAP and BMI values decreased insignificantly in tribal versus non-tribal individuals. Urbanization and age both contribute to an increase in CVD risk, although tribalism reduces risk more than nontribalism.

Figure 1. Location map of the surveyed area of the three districts of Jharkhand, India

Table 1A. Region-based Gender ratio of the total population surveyed

Area	Region	Gender		No. of participants	Total
		Male	Female		
Urban	Ranchi	124 (55.11%)	101 (44.89%)	225	487
	Patki (Bokaro)	65 (24.8%)	197 (75.2%)	262	
Rural	Karkat	52 (33.55%)	103 (66.45%)	155	345
	Khunti	56 (70%)	24 (30%)	80	
	Rest of Bokaro	61 (55.45%)	49 (44.55%)	110	
Total		358 (43.02%)	474 (56.98%)	832	

Table 1B. Region-based Age distribution of the total population surveyed

Area	Region	Age		Total
		<40 years	≥40 years	
Urban	Ranchi	67 (29.78%)	158 (70.22%)	225
	Patki (Bokaro)	155 (59.16%)	107 (40.84%)	262
Rural	Karkat	76 (49%)	79 (51%)	155
	Khunti	10 (12.50%)	70 (87.50%)	80
	Rest of Bokaro	54 (49.1%)	56 (50.9%)	110
Total		362 (43.50%)	470 (56.50%)	832

Table 1C. Region-based Ethnic groups distribution of the total population Surveyed

Area	Region	Ethnicity		Total
		Non-tribal	Tribal	
Urban	Ranchi	225 (100%)	0 (0%)	225
	Patki (Bokaro)	232 (88.55%)	30 (11.45%)	262
Rural	Karkat	0 (0%)	155 (100%)	155
	Khunti	0 (0%)	80 (100%)	80
	Rest of Bokaro	12 (11%)	98 (89%)	110
Total		469 (56.37%)	363 (43.63%)	832

Table 2. The modifiable (BMI, Hypertension, Blood Sugar Level) and non-modifiable (Age, Gender) risk factor characteristics changes in the studied contrasting categories in Rural and Urban Communities in Jharkhand

Characteristics	Category	Rural (N =345)	Urban (N = 487)	Total (N=832)
Age	≤ 40 Years	156	241	397
	≥ 41 Years	189	246	435
Gender	Male	169	189	358
	Female	176	298	474
BMI	≤ 24.9	288	356	644 (77.40%)
	≥ 25	57 (16.52%)	131 (26.89%)	188 (22.59%)
Hypertension (As per MAP Value)	Hypertensive (>100)	64 (18.55%)	202 (41.47%)	266 (31.96%)
	Normotensive (> 70, ≤ 100)	262	274	536
	Hypotensive (≤70)	19	11	30
Blood Sugar (Random Sugar) *	Non-Diabetic (<140 mg/dL)	117	225	342
	Pre-diabetic (≥ 140 to ≤199 mg/dL)	25 (16.12%)	77 (23.54%)	102 (21.16%)
	Diabetic ≥200 mg/dL)	13 (8.38%)	25 (7.46%)	38 (7.88%)

* Random Sugar was checked for 482 persons taking two regions out of a total of 832 participants. Value in the parenthesis shows the percentage of people having obesity or hypertension or pre-diabetes and diabetes.

Table 3. MLRA of the CVD risk factors in Rural and Urban regions **

Characteristics	Groups	High BMI OR (95% C.I.)	High MAP OR (95% C.I.)
Ethnicity	Non-tribal	Reference	Reference
	Tribal	0.84 (0.39-1.72)	0.70 (0.37-1.35)
Gender	Male	Reference	Reference
	Female	0.73 * (0.54-0.99)	0.85 (0.63-1.15)
Age	≤40 years	Reference	Reference
	>40 years	3.73 * (2.72-5.17)	1.31 * (0.98-1.76)
Region	Rural	Reference	Reference
	Urban	1.22 (0.57-2.52)	2.39 * (1.24-4.63)

*P value < 0.05

MLRA = multiple logistic regression analysis; CVD = Cardiovascular diseases

** Urban: Ranchi and Patki, Rural: Khunti, Karkat and rest of Bokaro

Table 4. MLR Analysis of High Blood Glucose Level as a Conventional CVD Risk Factor in Contrasting Non-modifiable Risk Factor Groups in urban and rural areas **

Characteristics	Groups	High Random Blood Glucose OR (95% C.I.)	
		Prediabetic	Diabetic
Ethnicity	Non-tribal	Reference	Reference
	Tribal	1.22 (0.51-2.97)	0.41 *(0.05-3.29)
Gender	Male	Reference	Reference
	Female	0.70 (0.43-1.14)	0.38 *(0.19-0.76)
Age	≤40 years	Reference	Reference
	>40 years	4.09 * (2.48-6.08)	3.59 *(1.67-7.73)
Region	Rural	Reference	Reference
	Urban	2.26 * (0.86-5.92)	1.58(0.07-4.89)

*P value < 0.05

MLRA = multiple logistic regression analysis; CVD = Cardiovascular diseases

** Rural:Karkat, Urban: Ranchi, and Patki

Table 5. Comparison of MLRA for conventional CVD risk factors (High BMI and MAP values) among Rural and Urban populations **

Characteristics		High BMI OR (95% C.I.)	High MAP OR (95% C.I.)
Ethnicity	Non-tribal	Reference	Reference
	Tribal	0.82(0.38-1.69)	0.71(0.37-1.36)
Gender	Male	Reference	Reference
	Female	0.66 *(0.47-0.93)	0.91(0.65-1.25)
Age	≤40 years	Reference	Reference
	>40 years	3.66 *(2.58-5.26)	1.36 *(0.98-1.88)
Region	Khunti & ROB	Reference	Reference
	Urban	1.32(0.61-2.82)	2.37 *(1.20-4.70)

*P value < 0.05

MLRA = multiple logistic regression analysis; CVD = Cardiovascular diseases

** Rural : Khunti and ROB villages;Urban: Ranchi and Patki of Bokaro

Table 6. Comparison of MLRA for conventional CVD risk factors (High BMI and MAP values) among Rural and Urban populations**

Characteristics	Groups	High BMI OR (95% C.I.)	High MAP OR (95% C.I.)
Ethnicity	Non-tribal	Reference	Reference
	Tribal	0.71 (0.33-1.47)	0.67 (0.35-1.29)
Gender	Male	Reference	Reference
	Female	0.82 (0.59-1.14)	0.83 (0.60-1.13)
Age	≤40 years	Reference	Reference
	>40 years	3.43 *(2.45-4.83)	1.23 (0.90-1.68)
Region	Karkat + ROB	Reference	Reference
	Urban	1.52 (0.70-3.22)	2.60 * (1.34-5.07)

*P value < 0.05

MLRA = multiple logistic regression analysis; CVD = Cardiovascular diseases

** Rural: Karkat and ROB villages; Urban: Ranchi and Patki of Bokaro

Table 7. Complete analysis using all covariates

Characteristics	Groups	High BMI OR (95% C.I.)	High MAP OR (95% C.I.)
Gender	Male	Reference	Reference
	Female	0.99 (0.59-1.68)	1.35 (0.80-2.30)
Age	≤40 years	Reference	Reference
	>40 years	2.94 *(1.81-4.83)	1.17 (0.72-1.89)
Region	Rural	Reference	Reference
	Urban	9.17 *(4.55-20.22)	8.04 *(4.34-14.63)
Smoking	No	Reference	Reference
	Yes	2.03 *(1.22-3.39)	0.96 (0.57-1.59)
Alcohol consumption	No	Reference	Reference
	Yes	1.30 (0.73-2.38)	1.85 *(1.06-3.27)
Exercise	No	Reference	Reference
	Yes	0.85 (0.50-1.46)	1.10(0.66-1.87)

*P value < 0.05

MLR analysis of Karkat and Rest of Bokaro villages as Rural with Ranchi and Patki of Bokaro as Urban communities

In this study of CVD risk factors, a nearly same trend of growth in hypertension and obesity was observed in a distinct set of rural villages and the same set of urban areas. More than 40-year-olds in these two places had a nearly 3.5-fold higher risk of being obese (OR = 3.43, 95% C. I. = 2.45-4.83) than lower-age group persons. Using Karkat as a reference, metropolitan regions had a 2.5-fold (significant) and 1.5-fold increased risk of developing hypertension and obesity, respectively. There was no substantial gender bias in vulnerability to developing hypertension or obesity in these populations (table 6). In this comparison, tribal populations exhibited a lower risk of acquiring hypertension than non-tribals. Table 6: Illustrations 1) The probabilities of being obese for the 'above 40 years age group' increase approximately 3.43 times those of the 'below 40 years age group'; 2) The odds of having a high MAP for the 'above 40 years age group' increase nearly 1.23 times that of the 'below 40 years age group'. As a result, age is an important determinant; 3) The odds of having a high MAP for urban people increased considerably more than 2.6 times that of rural people; and 4) The odds of having a high BMI increased insignificantly 1.52 times that of rural people. Hence, urbanization played a vital influence.

MLR Analysis using all the Covariates

The role of independent risk components, including behavioral risks, was evaluated using MLR analysis of examined abnormalities with all covariates. Though exercise has minimal influence, regular alcohol intake and smoking habits have made people nearly twice as likely to acquire hypertension or obesity, respectively. It was discovered that the probabilities of getting obesity were nearly three times greater in the 'over 40 years' age group than in the 'below 40 years' age group. When all factors were taken into account, urban people had a 9.17-fold and 8.04-fold higher risk of acquiring obesity and hypertension than rural people (table 7). Table 7 shows the results of MLR Analysis with all covariates, which showed odds of having high BMI and high MAP values for certain categories such as above 40 age, urbanized communities, smokers, and alcohol consumers, whereas gender and physical activities did not change the prevalence pattern of the two risk factors significantly. The odds of being obese and hypertensive in the urban population increase nearly ninefold and eightfold, respectively, compared to the rural population.

Discussion

CVD risk factors are individual characteristics that determine one's inadvertent susceptibility to one or more

types of cardiovascular disease. CVD risk factors have been found to vary by sociodemographics and ethnicity. As a result, understanding these determinants has been the first step in effectively tackling these disorders. In this cross-sectional survey, we attempted to recreate the context by incorporating two distinct demographic zones of Jharkhand: rural and urban, based on locations distant or near the two main state cities of Ranchi and Bokaro. This rural and urban area is primarily inhabited by tribal and nontribal communities, respectively.

In the general population, about 41.46%, 21.16%, and 31.95% of people had obesity, prediabetes, and hypertension, respectively, which is similar to a recent study in northeast India (16). Obesity, prediabetes, and hypertension were associated with CVD risk factors in the rural population at 16.52%, 16.12%, and 18.55%, respectively. In contrast, the urban population had a significantly greater percentage of obesity (59.13%) and hypertension (41.47%) as main risk factors, which were about four and two times higher than the rural share (table 2). Similarly, a larger proportion of urban people (23.54%) had a pre-diabetic tendency than rural people (16.12%). The percentage of diabetics did not differ significantly between rural and urban areas, with an overall prevalence of 7.88%, which was comparable to the finding (7.3%) obtained recently by ICMR in the fifteen states of India (20).

Several independent and dependent factors, singly or in different combinations under diverse environmental conditions, may impact the start of CVD of varying severity (21). MLR analysis was the ideal choice for assessing the contribution of numerous factors, individually or in combination, to the burden of this sick condition, as demonstrated in other relevant investigations (22).

MLR analysis of all covariates (total CVD risk factors) revealed a significantly higher risk of obesity (9 times) and hypertension (8 folds) for urban versus rural populations (table 7). This trend of an increasing number of persons in urban areas affected by one or more CVD risk factors is concerning, and it corresponds to the trajectory-change of CVD risk burden in developing South Asian nations such as India, which are experiencing fast urbanization (18).

Alcohol intake increased the risk of getting hypertension, while smoking increased the risk of acquiring obese (table 7). Such combined effects of alcohol use and smoking habits on CVD progression have been described both in India and elsewhere (23, 24).

We also compared the CVD risk factor prevalence trend in two other village populations to the urban population, and both comparisons revealed the similar pattern (tables 5 & 6). Our findings support the global picture of increasing tendency to develop CVD risk factors at a senior age of more than 40 years (25). The

'over 40 years' age group had a nearly 3.5-fold and 1.5-fold higher risk of acquiring obesity and hypertension than the 'below 40 years' age group. With increasing age, the risk of acquiring obesity increased about threefold (O. R: 2.94, C. I: 1.81-4.83) in the entire population across all locations and ninefold (O. R: 9.17, C. I: 4.55-20.22) in urban than rural populations (table 7). Similarly, the risk of getting hypertension increased nearly eightfold in urban versus rural populations (table 7).

Aside from chromosomal variations, sedentary lifestyles such as physical inactivity, deskbound job, and overeating are the most likely causes of the increased frequency of CVD risk factors in urban populations (26). Our previous report (27) did not show the same low diabetic and comparatively high pre-diabetic trend in rural Jharkhand. Intense physical labor for agriculture, a low-glycemic diet, and tribal people's genetic predisposition to obesity and hypertension may all minimize their risk of developing these conditions (28).

Conclusion

This paper examines the regional differences in CVD risk factors prevalent in Jharkhand, where 41.46% and 31.95% of people were obese and hypertensive. The urban stake in these two risk variables was nearly four and two times higher than the percentage held by rural residents. Though minimal diabetic change was detected, there was a higher incidence of prediabetes in urban regions (23.54%) compared to rural areas (16.12%). Multiple linear regression analysis with all factors revealed a direct 2-fold increased risk of developing hypertension and obesity with alcohol intake or smoking behaviors, respectively. MLRA also revealed that adults over the age of 40 had a nearly three-to-fourfold increased risk of developing obesity, prediabetes, or diabetes. MLR analysis that included all CVD risk factor variables revealed a larger fold increase in significant susceptibility to develop hypertension (O.R. = 8) or obesity (O.R. = 9) than the risk factors taken separately. This regional disparity in CVD risk prevalence in Jharkhand will help health organizations determine the true nature of the CVD burden in a certain location, allowing them to increase awareness and provide appropriate medical care.

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Ethics approval and consent for participation

The work was carried out in the Indian state of Jharkhand with the authorization of the Rajendra Institute of Medical Science's Ethical Committee in Ranchi (Protocol No. R94/22, IEC Registration No. ECR/769/INST/JH/2015/RR-21). Filled up Consent forms with the signatures of patients were collected.

Consent for Publication

Each study participant provided consent for the publication of their data.

Availability of Data and Material

All individual information and completed questionnaires are saved in case further questions arise.

Competing Interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors Contribution: A.A. was responsible for data gathering, fieldwork, and maintenance. D.G. statistically assessed and analyzed data, as well as established the theoretical and computational foundation for publication. AA and DG contributed approximately equally to preparing this work for publication. P.K. helped create the questionnaire model and assisted with the biochemical test and data analysis. Everyone contributed to the final manuscript. As a project mentor, S.G. contributed to the critical evaluation of the whole work and provided the manuscript with its final shape.

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